

WEB VULNERABILITY SCANNERS AND THEIR METHODS

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ABSTRACT

Throughout this article, you can learn about Web Vulnerability Scanners and general concepts about choosing the right ones. general information and their working principles, including what components they consist of. In this article you can get detailed information about OWASP Zed Attack Proxy (ZAP) and Arach. their most common types of attacks include: Brute Force, Fuzzing, Auto-tagging, Dynamic SSL Certificate and exc. The article is not primarily about choosing scanners that detect vulnerabilities because it also provides assumptions about what choices we should make depending on the type of vulnerability.

Methodology

An appropriate method was required to evaluate the chosen web vulnerability

scanners for this study. The preferred method process is shown in figure 2 below

Figure 2: Methodology process

The study was divided into different steps:

A. Benchmark selection:

To evaluate and test web application vulnerability scanners, an application that has the needed list of vulnerable test cases was needed so that true positive, true negatives, false positives, and false

negatives. A better decision in this selection required us to examine previous studies with the objective of getting an understanding of application benchmarking process as well as the existing benchmarks. Moreover, use the knowledge acquired from the examined studies for a better selection

of scanners to be tested as well as the benchmark to be used for the testing.

There are several benchmarks such as OWASP Benchmark and Web Application Vulnerability Scanner Evaluation Project (WAVSEP). For our experiment, we are using OWASP Benchmark.

B. Scanners Selection

While many previous studies have evaluated both commercial and free open source scanners, this study focuses on two free open source scanners including Arachni and OWASP ZAP.

A testing environment was created consisting of a local area network of two computers with one acting as a target and the other as the attacking computer. All useful applications necessary to perform the benchmarking which include OWASP Benchmark, OWASP ZAP, and Arachni, were installed. These programs were explored, and their different functionalities understood.

Scanners Overview

OWASP Zed Attack Proxy (ZAP)

OWASP ZAP is an easy to use scanner for finding vulnerabilities in web applications. It is one of the OWASP flagship projects that is recommended by OWASP for web applications vulnerability testing. ZAP is widely used by people ranging from security professionals, developers, and functional testers for automated security tests that can be incorporated into the continuous development environment. Additionally, ZAP is a free Open Source cross-platform scanner that is becoming a framework for advanced web application vulnerability testing[1].

Some of the ZAP features include:

Intercepting proxy, meaning that the browser can be configured to proxy through ZAP so that it can see all the request and responses which can also be changed.

ZAP provides both Passive and Active scanners. The passive scanner does not perform any attacks thus is safe to use on any web application. It runs all the time and examines the requests and responses but can still detect certain types of problems on that basis. The Active scanner, on the other hand, performs a wide range of attacks therefore formal permission is required for this to be used[2].

Spider, this is a ZAP feature that can be used to crawl the target application for missed and hidden pages and links.

Brute Force, Brute force is a trial and error method used to obtain information such as passwords and personal identification. By using OWASP DirBuster code, ZAP can find files that do not have links to them using the brute force component which is based on the dirbuster tool.

Fuzzing, ZAP can fuzz parameters and includes fuzzing libraries from the jbrofuzz and fuzz DB tools. This feature can be used to find more subtle vulnerabilities that the automated scanners might not detect.

Arachni

Arachni is a high-performance free Open Source ruby based framework that is aimed to help administrators and penetration testers evaluate the security of web applications. Arachni supports multiple platforms including Windows, Linux, and Mac OS X and can be instantly deployed using its portable packages[]. Arachni deployment options include: *Command Line Interface*(CLI) for quick scans, *Web User Interface*(WebUI) for multi-user, multi-scan

and multi-dispatcher management and distributed system with remote agents[4]. Some of the most important features of Arachni include:

Intelligence, a feature that enables Arachni to adapt to each web application on the fly, individual analysis of application resources which allows Arachni to customize requests to the used technologies.[5]

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